

Business Meeting

TEI Consortium Members' Meeting

September 19, 2019

Graz

Agenda

- Welcome and Opening of the Business Meeting (Kathryn Tomasek)
- Report from the Council (Martina Scholger)
- Report from the new Infrastructure Group (Martina Scholger)
- Report from the SIGs (Martina Scholger)
- Reports from TEI-C supported projects (Kathryn Tomasek)
 - TAPAS
 - jTEI
- Report from the Treasurer (Hugh Cayless)
- Report from the Membership Coordinator (Pip Willcox)
- Brief Questions for Members from the Board (Kathryn Tomasek)
- Election results (Pip Willcox)
- Announcing the Rahtz Prize Award (Kathryn Tomasek)
- Upcoming TEI-C Conference and Members' Meeting (Brian Pytlik Zillig)
- Thank Yous and Closing the Business Meeting (Kathryn Tomasek)

Report from Technical Council

Martina Scholger, Chair

Statistics for TEI-Guideline issues

As of 2019-09-19:

- 148 open issues on <https://github.com/TEIC/TEI>
- 100 issues closed since 2018-09-11 (last members' meeting)
- 113 issues created since 2018-09-11
 - Of those, 54 remain open, 59 have been closed
- 2018 had 199 issues the whole year

Statistics for TEI-Stylesheets issues

Regular cooperative stylesheets meetings

As of 2019-09-11:

- 120 open issues on <https://github.com/TEIC/Stylesheets>
- 49 issues closed since 2018-09-11 (last members' meeting)
- 58 issues created since 2018-09-11
 - Of those, 25 remain open, 33 have been closed

Since last we met in Tokyo

Two releases: Guidelines and Stylesheets

3.5.0 (January 2019): code name “Raven Release”

3.6.0 (July 2019): code name “Potrzebie”

- New elements to name, describe, identify objects
- New elements, attribute classes, and attributes to provide information about units of measurement
- Improvement of content models
- Rewriting and improvement of several sections of the Guidelines
- Fixing Bugs, adding new features
- More translations (especially Japanese)
- Wording improvements and corrections of typographic errors

F2F meeting

- Washington in May (see meeting [minutes](#))
- Graz in September (report coming soon)
 - Issues (Guidelines and Stylesheets)
 - Standoff discussion

teiHeader

text

TEI

teiHeader

standOff

model.listLike/annotationBlock/annotation

TEI

teiHeader

standOff

A new version of Roma (beta)

<https://romabeta.tei-c.org/>

- Roma “classic” remains in place until the new version reaches a more stable and complete status
- Please use it and let us know when you find issues, so we can move out of beta
- N.B. Only supports PureODD: no support for ODDs with RelaxNG
- Eventually will replace Roma “classic”, but we’ll keep it up at a different location
- Thinking big: **what should this tool do for you?** Leave a suggestion at the poster later! (or at <https://github.com/teic/romajs>)

Docker

<https://hub.docker.com/u/teic/>

Search Explore Help [Sign up](#) Sign in

Repos

teic
Text Encoding

teic/oxgarage public automated build	0 STARS	212 PULLS	> DETAILS
teic/teidev-docker public	1 STARS	73 PULLS	> DETAILS
teic/roma public automated build	0 STARS	37 PULLS	> DETAILS
teic/romajs public automated build	0 STARS	18 PULLS	> DETAILS

Help us help you

<https://github.com/TEIC/TEI/issues>

<https://github.com/TEIC/Stylesheets/issues>

Council works with the TEI Community!

Please raise issues on GitHub, post to the TEI-L mailing list, take part in discussions, test services, etc. This helps us to keep things moving.

Infrastructure Group

Martina Scholger

Infrastructure Group

- ADHO server crash in February
- Temporarily hosted by Compute Canada and in Paderborn
- Move to HumaNum
 - Website
 - Wiki
 - More services will be added soon (Roma, OxGarage, Debian packages, OJS)
- What's next
 - Mirroring services at other institutions

Report from SIGs

Martina Scholger, Technical Council Chair

Status of SIGs

- 10 active SIGs
 - Computer-Mediated Communication
 - Correspondence
 - East/Asian Japanese
 - Graph Technologies
 - Indic Texts
 - Manuscripts
 - Newspapers and Periodicals
 - Ontologies
 - TEI for Linguists
 - Text and Graphics
- 4 dormant SIGs
 - Education
 - Libraries
 - Scholarly Publishing
 - Tools
- 1 mission accomplished SIG
 - Music

Computer-Mediated Communication

Convener: Michael Beißwenger
Last F2F meeting in summer 2017

- 2017 at University of Duisburg-Essen (joint with a workshop on standards for corpora of computer-mediated communication).
- *CMC-core schema* - containing basic models necessary for the representation of CMC corpora - a documentation of the schema and a memorandum has been created.
- Beta-version will be made available on the SIGs website.
- Feature request to the TEI Council in late 2019.

Correspondence

Convener: Stefan Dumont, Sabine Seifert

Meeting at MM in Graz held by Peter Stadler

Main activities:

- Workshop “Challenges of Letter Encoding”
 - In October 2018 at the BBAW in Berlin
 - Organised by SIG Conveners and developers of DTA Base Format
 - Early Career Researchers
 - Discussion of issues, questions, phenomena concerning TEI encoding
- Preparation of a Handbook for TEI Encoding of Correspondence
 - Online publication of papers from the workshop discussing problems and possible solutions and Best practice
 - Open review by community before final publication
 - First papers expected at the end of the year

East Asian / Japanese

Convener: Kazuhiro Okada, Kiyonori
Nagasaki, Satoru Nakamura

- Established a Github account
 - <https://github.com/TEI-EAJ>
- TEI-guidelines for Japanese literature
- Developing and providing TEI tools
- Workshop on TEI encoding for Aozora-Bunko (= Japanese e-text distribution project)
- Monthly Guidelines-translation workshop
 - Google spreadsheet prepared by M. Holmes; remote participants
- Details will be presented at the TEI conference on Friday: “An Attempt of Dissemination of TEI in a TEI-underdeveloped country: Activities of the SIG EAJ”
- Next steps:
 - Keeping and extending the current activities
 - Including Korean and Chinese activities

Graph Technologies

Convener: Stefan Armbruster,
Andreas Kuczera, Iian Neill

- The SIG is working on a workflow for converting TEI-documents in a text-as-graph-model and vice versa.
- Workflow:
 - Convert XML TEI with neo4j to Standoff Property JSON

Manuscripts

Convener: Stephen McCormick and
Gerrit Brüning

- Discussion on how to revise chapter 11 of the TEI Guidelines in Tokyo
- <https://github.com/SteveWLU/TEI-MS-SIG/blob/master/ch-11-issues.md#forget-about-the-present-ch-11-for-a-moment>

Manuscripts

Convener: Stephen McCormick and
Gerrit Brüning

Meeting at MM in Graz co-chaired by
Yasmin Faghihi and Huw Jones
15 participants

- Discussion on joint Oxford-Cambridge efforts to produce a style guide for using TEI for manuscript description
- Discussion on how to propose additions to the Guidelines
- Specific issues
 - Texts such as extensive marginal and manuscript notes, diaries, notebooks etc.
 - How to encode palimpsests
 - Incorporating projects which only deal with discrete part of manuscripts such as bindings or manuscript notes
 - Issues arising from Fragmentarium to do with encoding fragments
- Share document for each area with SIG
 - formulating recommendations to the Council before the end of the year
 - enable projects (e.g. Fragmentarium) to move forward with TEI

Newspapers and Periodicals

Convener: Dario Kampkaspar

Meeting at MM in Graz

- New co-convener: Mary Isbell
- Need for an ontology describing parts of periodicals
- Preparation of call to TEI-L to share markup
- Preparation of a 1.5 day workshop on how to markup and name parts of periodicals.

Ontologies

Convener: Christian-Emil Ore

Meeting at MM in Graz

- New co-convener: Christopher Pollin
- New mailing list
- Common workspace
- Next steps
 - Data enrichment, information extraction
 - XSLT examples for transforming TEI to RDF
 - Alignment of TEI elements and upper level ontologies
 - Use cases of information extraction

TEI for Linguists

Conveners: Piotr Bański and Andreas Witt

Meeting at MM in Graz,

9 participants

- Brief presentation of TEI-related linguistic work from participants.
- Piotr informed about the current TEI-related initiatives ongoing and starting at ISO TC37 SC4 and within CLARIN.
- Tomaz Erjavec presented the Parla-CLARIN initiative
 - discussion providing translation tools from other formats
 - discussion on the @msd attribute (part of att.linguistic) and suggestion to introduce @msdRef in att.linguistic.
- Discussion on the addition of @orig and @norm to the set of basic descriptors on word level.
- Postulating the addition of <w> to att.lexicographic.
- Presentation of the planned proposal of new class “att.normalization”, providing the @norm and @orig attributes to both att.lexicographic and att.linguistic

TEI for Linguists

Conveners: Piotr Bański and Andreas Witt

Meeting at MM in Graz,
9 participants

- Presentation of the decision made by Council and invited experts on the context of the standOff element.
- The existing stdfSpec github repository will now be an alternative TEI customisation.
- The resolutions of the meeting are as follows:
 - to introduce a ticket proposing @msdRef
 - to finalize work on the existing ticket #1776 concerning @norm and @orig
 - to inform the linguistic community of the new standOff proposal and encourage people to try and encode linguistic standoff annotations in it, and to provide feedback on that to the Council

Text and Graphics

Conveners: Martin de la Iglesia and John Walsh

Meeting at MM in Graz

- Presentation of an application for annotating nested <zone> elements
- General discussion on positioning zones in non-TEI formats such as SVG and JSON and how to link coordinate data to TEI documents

Reports from TEI Supported Projects

TAPAS (TEI Archiving, Publication, and Access Service)

JTEI (Journal of the Text Encoding Initiative)

TAPAS 2018-19

Annual Update, TEI Members Meeting
Kathryn Tomasek for Julia Flanders

TAPAS: Current numbers

Users:

- about 152 new users since fall 2018
- about 28 new paid members since fall 2018

Classes and workshops using TAPAS this year:

- 3 workshops (ARL, DHSI, Boston College) totalling about 66 participants
- 1 semester-long course in progress
- 1 TAPAS training workshop planned for this fall

TAPAS: Next steps, 2019-2021

Pay off some “technical debt” and make new features visible

Increase TAPAS usage and membership (working with the TEI)

- Work on outreach and visibility
- Encourage workshop use and free TEI/TAPAS accounts

Start planning:

- Integration of TEI Processing into TAPAS
- Support for user schemas
- Community-led reading views and visualizations

Report from JTEI

Kathryn Tomasek

jTEI Updates: Editorial 1

Managing Editor

- Anne Baillot is stepping down after a three-year term.
 - We thank her for her service!
- At Anne's suggestion, a new team of managing editors has been chosen
 - Joel Kalvesmaki, Dumbarton Oaks Research Library
 - Pietro Liuzzo, University of Hamburg
 - Tiago Sousa Garcia, Newcastle University
 - Tanja Wissik, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities

jTEI Updates: Editorial 2

Publications

- Issue 10 publication completed in July 2019
- Issues 11 and 12 are currently being published and first sets of articles are available.
- First article in the Rolling Issue has been published.

To our members and readers

- Please send your submissions, keeping in mind we have three “genres” of articles: research papers, data sets, and project / tool notes;
- Please register as a reviewer;
- Current reviewers, please check your account and update email and keywords if necessary.
- See <http://journal.tei-c.org/journal/user/register> (register as reviewer)

jTEI Updates: Technical 1

Transition from ADHO server:

- Temporary OJS instance on a server that the Royal Academy of Dutch Language and Literature (Ghent, Belgium) rents from a commercial provider
- Updated the OJS instance from version 2.4.8 to 3.1.2
- Will move the OJS instance to the new TEI space at HumaNum
- jTEI Subversion repository has been migrated to HumaNum

jTEI Updates: Technical 2

Technical Work since 2018 meeting in Tokyo:

- XSLT stylesheets (<https://github.com/TEIC/Stylesheets/commits/dev/profiles/jtei>):
 - improvement of punctuation handling in quoted text, now as much compliant with CMOS as possible
 - addition of SVN revision information to OpenEdition and PDF output (in hidden places), in order to provide a way of checking the version of articles at <https://journals.openedition.org/jtei> during (and after) the final proofing stage
- jTEI ODD (https://github.com/TEIC/TEI/commits/dev/P5/Exemplars/tei_jtei.odd):
 - refined Schematron checks w.r.t. end-punctuation in footnotes and bibliography
- oxygen-tei (<https://github.com/TEIC/oxygen-tei/commits/master/oxygen-tei>):
 - updated class paths for transformation scenarios to latest Oxygen release
- internal Oxygen project:
 - refined project-internal Schematron checks for tighter editing control
 - added some clean-up and normalization transformation scenarios for easier conversion from DOCX to jTEI XML

Finance Report

Annual Meeting 2019 — Hugh Cayless

Year-over-Year Cash Profit & Loss

	Jan - Dec 14	Jan - Dec 15	Jan - Dec 16	Jan - Dec 17	Jan - Dec 18	Jan - Aug 19
Ordinary Income/Expense						
Income						
Membership Dues	72,997.00	62,672.00	56,278.35	69,307.40	52,925.87	24,992.61
Miscellaneous Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	50.00	70.00
Interest	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	468.08	299.00
Total Income	72,997.00	62,672.00	56,278.35	69,307.40	53,443.95	25,361.61
Gross Profit	72,997.00	62,672.00	56,278.35	69,307.40	53,443.95	25,361.61
Expense						
Total Contract Services	5,106.00	0.00	1,801.50	11,137.00	20,915.00	10,535.00
Total Operations	39,429.00	18,193.96	33,326.12	4,901.23	54,739.29	3,987.18
Total Other Types of Expenses	1,000.00	1,848.00	2,878.00	1,492.26	1,000.93	1,000.00
Total Travel and Meetings	25,741.00	9,789.24	32,445.26	19,857.83	47,532.27	20,333.40
Total Expense	71,276.00	29,831.20	70,450.88	37,388.32	124,187.49	35,855.58
Net Ordinary Income	1,721.00	32,840.80	-14,172.53	31,919.08	-70,743.54	-10,493.97
Net Income	1,721.00	32,840.80	-14,172.53	31,919.08	-70,743.54	-10,493.97
Beginning Cash	186,119.00	187,840.00	220,806.12	209,461.07	241,923.73	171,180.19
Ending Cash	187,840.00	220,680.80	206,633.59	241,923.73	171,180.19	160,686.22

Partial Expenses Break Down 2018

- Travel and meetings: \$47,532
- Finance and Accounting Services: \$19,500
- Insurance, Legal, Accounting Fees: \$1,415
- Copy Editing: \$717
- Bank Fees: \$1,489
- Wild Apricot: \$1,080 (note: we upped our membership level this year)
- JTEI Managing Editor: \$20,000 (one-time payment)
- TAPAS: \$30,000 (2 years' support)

Balance Sheet (for 2019, Jan-Aug)

	<u>Aug 31, 2019</u>
ASSETS	
Current Assets	
Checking/Savings	
Citizens Checking	57,602
Citizens Money Market	100,757
Paypal	2,327
Total Checking/Savings	<u>160,686</u>
Accounts Receivable	
Accounts Receivable	56,599
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>56,599</u>
Total Current Assets	<u>217,285</u>
TOTAL ASSETS	<u>217,285</u>
LIABILITIES & EQUITY	
Liabilities	
Current Liabilities	
Accounts Payable	
Accounts Payable	1,542
Total Accounts Payable	<u>1,542</u>
Other Current Liabilities	
Deferred Revenue	26,425
Total Other Current Liabilities	<u>26,425</u>
Total Current Liabilities	<u>27,967</u>
Total Liabilities	27,967
Equity	
Opening Balance Equity	2,953
Unrestricted Net Assets	166,700
Net Income	19,665
Total Equity	<u>189,318</u>
TOTAL LIABILITIES & EQUITY	<u>217,285</u>

2019 Snapshot: Actual vs. Budget

	Jan - Aug 19	Budget	\$ Over Budget	% of Budget
Ordinary Income/Expense				
Income				
Total Income	25,062.61	24,500.00	562.61	102.3%
Gross Profit	25,062.61	24,500.00	562.61	102.3%
Expense				
Total Contract Services	10,535.00	12,380.00	-1,845.00	85.1%
Total Operations	3,987.18	1,250.00	2,737.18	318.97%
Total Other Types of Expenses	1,000.00	2,500.00	-1,500.00	40.0%
Total Travel and Meetings	20,333.40	15,000.00	5,333.40	135.56%
Total Expense	35,855.58	31,130.00	4,725.58	115.18%
Total Other Income	299.00	280.00	19.00	106.79%
Net Other Income	299.00	280.00	19.00	106.79%
Net Income	-10,493.97	-6,350.00	-4,143.97	165.26%

Summary

- The TEI is in good financial shape. We have enough reserves to keep operating for some time even if our income dried up (no sign of that happening).
- We spent a lot of money last year. Some of it was catch-up, some one-time expense, and travel for the Tokyo meeting was more than we usually spend (but a good investment, I think).
- Council meetings remain our single largest expense, and we spend more than we used to. Fewer Council members have financial support from their institutions. But that also means we're not restricted in where Council members come from
- We actually have a budget! Still need to work on refining it as a useful planning instrument.

Report from the Membership Coordinator

Pip Willcox

Membership (active, paid-up members)

Sustaining Partner (\$5,000)	3
Patron (\$2,500)	4
Friend (\$1,500)	8
Contributor (\$500)	17
Supporter (\$250)	23
Individual (\$50)	150
Free (workshop, for 1 year)	152

Workshop Memberships

- The TEI will provide free memberships for one year for participants in publicly announced, open enrollment workshops.
- Send a spreadsheet listing participant names, email addresses and affiliations to the Membership Coordinator or the Treasurer.

Membership via Donation

- Prospective members of the TEI who cannot afford the \$50 annual fee can join by making a donation in any amount.
- Donors who want to be members should simply write 'membership' in the comment field on the submission form so the Treasurer will know they want their individual membership activated.

Questions for the Membership

Kathryn Tomasek and Christiane Fritze

Preferred Mode of Contact

We had a question from a member about how best to contact the membership with announcements from the Board.

Our usual mode of contact has been to post to the list when we have announcements of nominations, calls for proposals to host the annual conference and members' meetings, and so forth.

The notion that we should also email members with these kinds of communications.

We would like to hear from you on this question. We have time for no more than 5 minutes' discussion today.

TEI-C Website Projects Page

We are currently undertaking a revision of the Projects Page, which seems rather out of date. We have two matters to present, with again, only 5 minutes for discussion:

Does the membership want this [page](https://tei-c.org/activities/projects/) (https://tei-c.org/activities/projects/)?

If so, please help us update this page by completing this form, which will be linked from the website Projects Page:

<https://preview.tinyurl.com/TEIprojectsForm>

Election Results

Pip Willcox for the Nominating and Elections Committee

Gimena del Rio Riande, Christiane Fritze, Hugh Cayless, and Luis Meneses, with Scott Hamlin for TAPAS

Overview

- <https://www.opavote.com>
 - 3 August 2019
 - 17 September 2019 at 23:59 HST
 - 46 days
-
- Board: 4 candidates - 2 positions
 - Council: 7 candidates - 6 positions
 - TAPAS Advisory Board: 1 candidates - 1 position

TEI-C Elections 2019 - Individual Members

In 2019, TEI Members will hold an election to fill 6 open positions on the TEI Technical Council and 2 on the TEI Board of Directors; each newly elected member will serve a two-year term, 2020 and 2021. We are also electing 1 new member to the TAPAS Advisory Board. The following persons have been nominated to the TEI Nominating Committee and have agreed to stand as candidates for election to the TEI Technical Council, the TEI Board, and the TAPAS Advisory Board respectively. The nominees have each supplied a statement covering two aspects:

1. their reasons for wishing to serve on the Board, Technical Council or TAPAS Advisory Board and their particular goals.
2. a brief biography focusing on relevant research, practice, education, training, etc.

The statements and biographical descriptions for the candidates can be accessed [here](#).

A Note on Voting

Voting will be conducted via the OpaVote website, which uses the open-source balloting software OpenSTV for tabulation. OpenSTV is a widely used open-source Single Transferable Vote program.

TEI Member voters, identified by email address, will receive a URL at which to cast their ballots. Upon closing of the election, all voters who cast a vote will be sent an email with a link to the results of the election, from which it is also possible to download the actual final ballots for verification. Individual members may vote in the TEI Technical Council elections. The nominated representative of institutions with membership may vote for both the TEI Board and TEI Technical Council.

Voting closes on September 17, 2019 at 23:59 Hawaii-Aleutian Standard Time (HAST) as it offers the latest global midnight.

Turnout

In total we had 100 votes. A small improvement from the 97 votes for last year:

- 78 from Individual members (out of 150 - 52% turnout)
- 22 from Institutional members (out of 41 - 54% turnout)

Election Results

- Board
 - James Cummings and Kathryn Tomasek.
- Council
 - Elisa Beshero-Bondar, Meaghan J. Brown, Jessica H. Lu, Martina Scholger, Peter Stadler, and Magdalena Turska.
- TAPAS Advisory Board
 - Mary Isbell

Congratulations!

Big thanks to those whose terms will end in December 2019!

Board

- Georg Vogeler, University of Graz

Council

- James Cummings, Newcastle University
- Elli Mylonas, Brown University
- Sarah Stanley, Florida State University

Rahtz Prize for TEI Ingenuity 2019

Awards Panel Members: Kathryn Tomasek, Martina Scholger, Sabine Seifert, and Stefan Dumont

2019 Rahtz Prize

TEI Boilerplate

John Walsh, Grant Simpson, Saeed Moaddeli

**TEI
BOILERPLATE**

<http://dcl.ils.indiana.edu/teibp/>

TEI-C Conference

Lincoln, Nebraska

October 2020

Nebraska: Where the American West Begins

<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jp7JKz0KxJE>

Important Dates

- TEI Council and Board meetings:
Oct 24-26
- Workshops: Oct. 26-27, 2020
- Conference proper: Oct. 28-30, 2020

<http://cdrh.unl.edu>

Brett Barney

Matt Cohen

Amanda Gailey

Andy Jewell

Ken Price

Brian Pytlik Zillig

Steve Ramsay

Laura Weakly

Lincoln, Nebraska

Population ~300,000

Conference Hotels

- Embassy Suites: Main hotel
- Others available:
 - Cornhusker Marriott
 - Courtyard by Marriott
 - Hyatt Place

Easy walking distance
to all venues and to
restaurants

Night Life

KRADDY, ARCHNEMESIS,
BASSTHOVEN

BOURBON THEATRE
LINCOLN, NE
TUESDAY, FEBRUARY 8TH

Hotel Near University of Nebraska-Lincoln and the Center for Digital Research in the Humanities

Registration opens in
July 2020

Looking forward to seeing you in
October 2020!

Newcastle Upon Tyne, United Kingdom

September 2021

- **Travel:** Well-connected airport and rail, very easy to get to! City is walkable but also has great metro system to the coast and nearby cities
- **Venue:** Excellent conference facilities
- **Location:** Lots of hotels, restaurants and pubs!
- **Tourism:** Lots of Art Galleries, Museums, Hadrian's Wall, and the North-East has more castles than any other part of England
- **People:** "Geordies" are extremely friendly
- **Local Organisers:** James Cummings, Adam Mearns, Tiago Sousa Garcia

TEI 2021

@tei2021
tei2021@newcastle.ac.uk

Newcastle Upon Tyne, United Kingdom

We look forward to giving you a friendly
Geordie welcome to Newcastle University
in September 2021!

Danke schön!

Thank you!

Local Committee

- Elisabeth Raunig
- Walter Scholger
- Martina Scholger
- Elisabeth Steiner
- Georg Vogeler

Sponsors

- University of Graz
- Centre for Information-Modelling, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities
- CLARIAH-AT
- City of Graz
- SyncroSoft

TEI2019 Program Committee, 1

- Georg Vogeler, Chair, University of Graz
- Gimena del Rio Riande, Chair, SECRIIT-IIBICRIT, LINHD-UNED, Spain; University of Buenos Aires, Argentina
- Elisa Beshero-Bondar, University of Pittsburgh
- James Cummings, University of Newcastle
- Vanessa Bigot Juloux, Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes (EPHE), Paris Sciences et Lettres (PSL)
- Research associate, Institute of Archaeology (Andrews University, Michigan)
- Syd Bauman, Northeastern University Library
- Magdalena Turska, eXist Solutions
- Kiyonori Nagasaki, University of Tokyo
- Kathryn Tomasek, Wheaton College Massachusetts
- Laurent Romary, INRIA
- Luis Meneses, University of Victoria
- Martina Scholger, University of Graz

TEI2019 Program Committee, 2

- Hugh Cayless, Duke University
- Martin Holmes, University of Victoria
- José Calvo Tello, University of Würzburg
- Claudia Resch, Austrian Academy of Sciences
- Julia Flanders, Northeastern University Library
- Franz Fischer, Università Ca' Foscari Venezia
- Frank Fischer, Higher School of Economics Moscow
- Susanne Haaf, Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities
- Susanna Alles, University of Miami
- Pip Wilcox, University of Oxford
- Christiane Fritze, Austrian National Library
- Roman Bleier, University of Graz
- Walter Scholger, University of Graz

2019 TEI Technical Council

- Martina Scholger, 2019 Chair, University of Graz (2019)
- Syd Bauman, Northeastern University (2020)
- Elisa Beshero-Bondar, University of Pittsburgh (2019)
- Hugh Cayless, Duke University (2020)
- James Cummings, Newcastle University (2019)
- Vanessa Bigot Juloux, Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes (2020)
- Elli Mylonas, Brown University (2019)
- Peter Stadler, University of Paderborn (2019)
- Sarah Stanley, Florida State University (2020)
- Magdalena Turska, Oxford University (2019)
- Raffaele Viglianti, University of Maryland (2020)

2019 TEI Board

- Elected

- Kathryn Tomasek, Chair, Wheaton College, Massachusetts (2019)
- Christiane Fritze, Secretary, Austrian National Library (2020)
- Gimena del Rio Riande, Seminario de Edicion y Critica Textual (SECRIT-IIBICRIT) (2020)
- Pip Willcox, The National Archives – UK (2020)
- Georg Vogeler, University of Graz (2019)

- Ex officio

- Hugh Cayless, Treasurer, Duke University
- Martina Scholger, Council Chair, University of Graz
- Luis Meneses, Webmaster, University of Victoria

